

Multiscale modeling of VOC-graphene nanostructure interactions: designing new sorbents for portable mass spectrometric applications

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Abstract

In this study, we conducted an extensive computational investigation using various theoretical approaches to elucidate the molecular-level interactions between ten representative volatile organic compounds (VOCs) and functionalized graphene nanosheets. Our objective was to identify graphene modifications capable of binding the selected VOCs, which are otherwise challenging to trap and analyze in portable membrane inlet mass spectrometric (MIMS) systems. This computational study employed a combination of semiempirical and quantum mechanical calculations complemented by molecular dynamics (MD) simulations. Semiempirical quantum mechanical calculations were performed using the GFN2-xTB method to obtain binding energy information between VOCs and nanostructures. Quantum mechanical calculations based on density functional theory (DFT) with selected density functionals were utilized to study the most important local reactivity descriptors and to analyze the intermolecular noncovalent interactions. Additionally, MD simulations were employed further to evaluate the binding and desorbing capabilities of the selected system. The findings of our study suggest that graphene surfaces functionalized with OH groups have significant potential to serve as a foundation for designing new sorbents capable of efficiently trapping butyric and isobutyric acids in portable MIMS systems.

Keywords: MIMS, sorbents, VOC, graphene, GFN2-xTB, GFN-FF, MD, DFT

1. Introduction

Volatile organic compounds (VOCs) are small molecular structures (< 350 Da), which evaporate at room temperature (25 °C) and pressure of 760 mmHg. According to their origin, they can be endogenous (i.e., biogenic) or exogenous (i.e., anthropogenic). VOCs are widely present in the world – all living organisms emit them and are also produced during various industrial processes, etc. Therefore, they can provide insight into ecosystems, the metabolism of various organisms, bioreactions, etc. A new area of experimentation called volatilomics address analysis of these compounds in biosystems [1]. Specifically interesting are VOCs present in the exhaled human breath. These volatile metabolites can cross a blood-air barrier in the lungs and provide instant insight into the organism's state [2]. Mainly examined are exhaled VOCs that could be used to diagnose certain pulmonary diseases (asthma, COPD, pulmonary cancer, etc.) [3]. However, there are indices that certain breath VOCs could serve as biomarkers for general organism status monitoring – acetone and isoprene for physical activity rate [4–6], acetone, isoprene, n-pentane for metabolic disorders like diabetes mellitus and cardiovascular diseases [7,8], acetone, ethanol, isoprene, n-pentane, acetic acid, propanoic acid, butyric acid for nutritional status [2,9]. Assessment of food and lifestyle habits impacts by breath VOCs determination is a new and exciting research niche [10,11]. It has the potential to be used as a screening diagnostics in nutritional offices and to provide some preliminary results prior to conventional analyses. These results would help make personalized recommendations for the improvement of diet and lifestyle [12].

Conventionally, VOCs are determined by gas chromatography with mass spectrometry (GC-MS) technique. This technique has been well-known for a long time and represents a standard for determining volatile compounds [1]. However, as VOCs are highly labile analytes, sample transport from the sampling place to the laboratory is challenging. Therefore, it would be more desirable to conduct VOC analysis *on-site*. GC-MS cannot be used for in-field analysis, as the instrument is bulky and requires strict laboratory conditions. Thus, developing and employing smaller, portable VOC determination systems is desirable [1].

Membrane inlet mass spectrometry (MIMS) is a well-known technique used for VOCs analysis in different applications – monitoring of chemical reactors and industrial processes [13], environmental monitoring [14], human chemical signature determination [15], homeland security [16], breath analysis [12]. MIMS is based on the process of pervaporation [17]. In this process, volatile analytes are absorbed in the selective membrane, diffuses through it, and later desorbed into the mass spectrometric system, placed in the vacuum. MIMS system recently validated for the exhaled breath VOCs analysis combines polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) based membrane selective for volatile organic compounds, electron impact (EI) ionization and single quadrupole (Q) mass analyzer [12]. It enables online and offline analysis, with sensitivity at low

ppb levels. It provides a full scan across the mass range 0-300 m/z , with a short analysis time (about 1-2 min).

Additionally, it enables a selected ion monitoring (SIM) with a very fast response time [12]. However, a MIMS system does not provide separation (e.g., chromatographic) of analytes in time by itself. This represents a challenge in determining VOCs with similar structures and/or shared mass fragments in the EI ionization process, commonly used in MIMS. Therefore, a MIMS system could be coupled with a temperature programmed desorption (TPD) device. This would enable that selected VOCs get to the mass analyzer individually and be successfully analyzed.

Previously, several VOCs characteristic for exhaled breath were separated using the MIMS system coupled with TPD and employing known and commercially available sorbents (Tenax TA[®], HayeSep D[®]) [18]. Selected VOCs separation was achieved, but the peaks were wide, and their shapes were not satisfying for this methodology's potential future extensive usage [18]. It would be impossible to use this system to separate more VOCs. This is especially important when VOCs in natural biogenic samples (i.e., exhaled breath) are examined – as the exclusion of interfering compounds from the sample is impossible. Additionally, using listed sorbents to separate analytes in numerous consecutive analyses is impossible. Thus, we aim to investigate alternative approaches to overcome this limitation of MIMS and enable more comprehensive employment in VOC analysis originating from biosystems.

Atomistic calculations play a pivotal role in computational science, allowing researchers to delve into the atomic-level behavior of matter. These calculations are indispensable for advancing knowledge and fostering innovation across a broad range of scientific and technological disciplines. By enabling predictions of material properties and behavior prior to synthesis or production, atomistic calculations offer a significant advantage, conserving valuable time and resources [19–22]. When combined with experimental findings, they facilitate a comprehensive understanding of phenomena, serving as a fundamental starting point for analyzing novel molecules and materials [23–29]. Scientists have a diverse array of theoretical levels at their disposal, empowering them to investigate atomic mechanisms with great flexibility [30–34].

In this work, an extensive multiscale modeling study was conducted to understand the interactions between the most relevant food metabolism-related exhaled VOCs and 2D nanostructures based on graphene at the molecular level. The overall objective of this study was to identify possible modifications of the graphene surface that could be utilized as a sorbent for binding VOCs that are typically difficult to isolate in portable membrane-inlet mass spectrometric systems (MIMS).

Specifically, ten highly representative VOCs were considered, which are known to be emitted into the air through human exhalation: 1-propanol, 2-propanol, acetic acid, acetone, butyric acid, isobutyric acid, ethanol, isoprene, n-pentane, and propionic acid. The interactions of these VOCs were examined with four graphene-based nanosheets: pristine graphene, graphene nanosheet modified with holes, graphene nanosheet modified with oxygen, and graphene nanosheet modified with OH group. The investigation aimed to discover whether proposed functionalizations of graphene nanosheet might lead to improved binding of some VOCs that are otherwise difficult to capture, release and analyze by the MIMS.

2. Computational Details

Geometrical optimizations of graphene nanosheet derivatives have been performed using the GFN2-xTB method, developed by Prof. Grimme and coworkers [35–39]. Further, these structures were subjected to single point energy calculations at the DFT level of theory, using B3LYP density functional [40–43] and 6-31G(d,p) basis set, to obtain information about the molecular electrostatic potential (MEP) and average local ionization energies (ALIE).

Systems where VOC molecules interact with graphene nanosheet derivatives have been geometrically optimized using the GFN2-xTB method. Due to the small size, the VOC molecules were geometrically optimized at the DFT level of theory, with B3LYP density functional [40–43] and 6-31G(d,p) basis set, followed by frequency calculations to ensure that the proper ground states were identified.

Molecular dynamics (MD) simulations were performed using the GFN-FF method [44], also developed by Prof. Grimme and coworkers. The simulation time was set to 1000 ps, while all other MD simulation parameters took values suggested for the GFN-FF method, available in the official documentation of the xtb program [45].

Binding energies between the graphene nanosheet derivatives and the VOC molecules were calculated at the GFN2-xTB level of theory using the following equation:

$$E_i = E_{tot}(GR + VOC) - E(GR) - E(VOC), \quad (1)$$

where $E_{tot}(GR + VOC)$ denotes the total energy of the optimized complex consisting of a graphene nanosheet derivative and the VOC molecule, $E(GR)$ denotes the total energy of the optimized graphene nanosheet derivative, while the $E(VOC)$ denotes the total energy of VOC molecule.

GFN2-xTB calculations and MD simulations based on the GFN-FF method were performed as implemented in the xtb 6.5.1. program. GFN2-xTB calculations were run within the

atomistica.online molecular modeling platform [46], freely available at <https://atomistica.online>. GFN-FF MD simulations were performed with the xtb program installed locally on the workstation. DFT calculations were performed with the Jaguar program [47–50], as implemented in the Schrödinger Materials Science Suite 2022-2. The Jaguar program was used to generate MEP and ALIE surfaces and identify and quantify noncovalent interactions.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Studied molecular models and their ground-state geometries

We start our study by providing information about the models used for various calculations performed in this study and their ground-state geometries. The models of graphene-based nanosheets investigated as potential sorbents for selected VOC molecules were referred to in the manuscript using the following names: **GR** (pristine graphene nanosheet), **GR-hole** (graphene nanosheet with a hole in the center), **GR-O** (graphene nanosheet with an oxygen atom attached in the center), and **GR-OH** (graphene nanosheet with an OH group attached in the center). The ground state geometries of these sorbents and their characteristic bond lengths are presented in Figure 1. Conversely, Figure 2 contains ground state geometries of the VOC molecules studied in this work.

Figure 1. Ground state geometries of sorbents a) **GR**, b) **GR-hole**, c) **GR-O** and d) **GR-OH**

The pristine graphene nanosheet model used as a basis for designing derivatives consisted of 130 carbon atoms. To compensate for the dangling bonds as a consequence of the extraction of

the model from an infinite 2D honeycomb structure of graphene, hydrogen atoms were attached to the edge carbon atoms. Taking everything into account and depending on the type of functionalization, the considered sorbent nanosheets consisted of 180 – 200 atoms. For these reasons, geometrical optimizations were performed using the semiempirical quantum mechanical calculations based on the GFN2-xTB method.

Considering the structural properties, the GFN2-xTB method is a highly accurate semiempirical method derived from the DFT approach, which takes only a fraction of the computational time to optimize structures compared to standard DFT methods combined with standard basis sets. Since our molecular systems consisted of more than 200 atoms, it was the reliable method we could apply to obtain accurate geometries at the quantum-mechanical level.

Geometrically optimized structures were checked for characteristic bond lengths, and the well-known values have been reproduced without problems. In Figure 1a, it can be seen that the well-known bond length between carbon atoms of 1.42 Å was obtained. The longer diameter of the hole in the middle of the graphene nanosheet obtained by removing one carbon atom was equal to 4.76 Å (Figure 1b). In the case of the graphene nanosheet modified with an oxygen atom, Figure 1c, the bond length between the carbon and oxygen atom was 1.41 Å. Finally, in the case of the graphene nanosheet with the attached OH group, Figure 1d, the C-O bond length was measured to be 1.44 Å, while the O-H bond length was measured to be 0.97 Å.

Geometries obtained using the GFN2-xTB method were further used for DFT calculations with B3LYP-D3 density functional and MIDIX basis set, to obtain DFT-level accurate electron density for the analysis required to identify noncovalent interactions between sorbents and VOC molecules. Conversely, dispersion dispersion-corrected version of the B3LYP functional (the B3LYP-D3) is a reliable approach for DFT calculations on systems containing molecules that interact via noncovalent interactions.

Figure 2. Ground state geometries of breath VOC molecules

The size of breath VOC molecules allowed the application of DFT calculations based on the B3LYP density functional in combination with a 6-31G(d,p) basis set. The ground state geometries are presented in Figure 2. Ground state geometries of considered sorbents and VOC molecules have been combined to obtain systems consisting of one sorbent structure and one VOC molecule. These systems were then optimized using the GFN2-xTB method, followed by calculations of binding energies. Before passing on the results regarding binding energies, we will discuss the effects of functionalizations of graphene nanosheets considering the two quantum molecular descriptors.

3.2. Reactive properties of functionalized graphene nanosheets

We continue our study by analyzing the effects of various functionalizations of graphene nanosheets on their local reactive properties. Geometrically optimized pristine and functionalized graphene nanosheets were subjected to single-point energy calculations using B3LYP functional and MIDIX basis set to obtain information on local reactivity descriptors.

Understanding the local reactivity of molecular structures is crucial in various fields, and it can be achieved by applying various reactivity tools. Herein, we applied two key descriptors, namely the MEP and ALIE, in comprehending the local reactivity of molecules and the influence of specific functional groups on their reactivity. By analyzing the MEP, we gain insights into the distribution of electron density and electrostatic potential, enabling the identification of the molecular sites susceptible to interactions based on the electrostatics. By examining ALIE, we also elucidate the ease of removing an electron from specific atomic sites, thereby understanding sites susceptible to chemical reactions and electron transfer processes. These two descriptors helped us to understand how modifications of graphene nanosheets affected the reactivity, offering the possibility later to understand the binding of various VOC molecules.

Figure 3. Distribution of MEP and ALIE values a) GR, b) GR-hole, c) GR-O and d) GR-OH

We used the same interval for the color scale for all systems to compare MEP and ALIE surfaces visually. Of all calculated MEP values, the lowest and the highest were -39.52 kcal/mol and +32.56 kcal/mol, respectively, so values of -40 and +33 kcal/mol have been used as extreme values for the MEP color scale. On the other side, the lowest and the highest calculated ALIE were 153.64

kcal/mol and 336.43 kcal/mol, respectively, so values of 153 kcal/mol and 337 kcal/mol have been taken as extreme values for the ALIE color scale. Numerical values of the lowest and highest values of these descriptors have been summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Minimal and maximal values of MEP and ALIE descriptors

	Minimal MEP	Maximal MEP	Minimal ALIE	Maximal ALIE
GR	-12.97	24.34	205.97	334.05
GR-hole	-36.06	25.24	153.64	335.72
GR-O	-30.81	24.72	205.01	336.43
GR-OH	-39.52	32.56	208.05	333.87

Results presented in Figure 3 indicate that all three modifications considered in this study led to drastic changes in the extreme values of MEP. Considering the negative MEP values, the magnitude tripled in almost all cases, while the magnitude of the positive values increased insignificantly in cases of GR-hole and GR-o derivatives. According to the results from Figure 3 and Table 1, the most significant change in charge distribution occurred when the graphene nanosheet was modified with the OH group. In this case, the magnitude of the lowest MEP value more than tripled, while the magnitude of the highest MEP value increased by almost 30%. Overall, results related to the MEP descriptor indicate that the considered modifications of the graphene nanosheet severely affect its possibilities to interact with other molecules based on electrostatic interactions.

An interesting situation also happened when the ALIE descriptor was analyzed. When the graphene nanosheet was modified with the hole in its center, the minimal value of ALIE drastically decreased by more than 50 kcal/mol. This result indicates that this type of structural alteration drastically increases the sensitivity of graphene toward electrophilic attacks. In all other cases, the minimal values of the ALIE descriptor changed minimally.

3.3. Binding energies

We initiated the identification of optimal candidates for designing new sorbents for VOCs by examining the ground state geometries of the studied systems consisting of graphene nanosheet derivative and VOC molecule. Our first objective was to determine the binding energies between the mentioned VOCs and graphene-based nanosheets. To achieve this, we constructed systems consisting of a single VOC molecule positioned above the surface of each graphene-based nanosheet. The polymer employed in a commercial sorbent known as TENAX[®] was taken as a reference system, so the binding energies between one chain of 2,6-diphenyl-p-phenylene oxide (PPPO, the principal component of TENAX[®]) and VOC molecules were also calculated. This resulted in a total of 50 molecular systems, as each of the ten molecules was placed above each

of the four graphene-based nanosheets and **PPPO**. We subsequently optimized the geometry of each system and calculated the corresponding binding energy.

Due to the large size of these systems, which comprised between 180 and 200 atoms, it was necessary to employ a semiempirical quantum mechanical level of theory for the geometry optimizations and binding energy calculations. In this regard, we applied the GFN2-xTB method, known for its remarkable accuracy relative to the computational time required when compared to standard DFT methods. In Figure 4, we present two representative optimized geometries corresponding to the binding of isobutyric acid on the **PPPO** chain and **GR-OH** nanosheet.

Figure 4. Optimized geometries of isobutyric **binding** on a) **PPPO** chain and b) **GR-OH** nanosheet

In Figure 4, for clarity, adsorber structures (**PPPO** chain and **GR-OH**) are presented in wired representation, while isobutyric acid, along with the interacting OH group, is presented in ball and stick representation. Negative binding energies indicated attractive interaction between the VOC molecule and adsorber in all cases. Figure 5 presents the magnitudes of binding energies between VOC molecules and adsorbers. **Binding energies have also been summarized in a tabulated form in Table S1 of the Supplementary Materials.**

Figure 5. Magnitudes of binding energies between VOC molecules and considered adsorbents

PPPO is the main active component of the well-known commercially available TENAX[®] sorbent. Therefore, in Figure 5, the magnitudes of binding energies of various graphene-based nanostructures have been compared with **PPPO**. In almost all cases, it is evident that **PPPO** binds the considered VOC molecules more strongly than pristine graphene. Only two VOC molecules bind more strongly to graphene than **PPPO**, but the binding energy in these cases is very similar. Therefore, according to the calculated binding energies, modifications of graphene are necessary to make it suitable for binding the considered VOC molecules.

In most cases, the presence of a defect in the form of a hole in the center of the graphene nanosheet did not improve the binding energies compared to the binding of VOC molecules to **PPPO**. In some cases, this defect did improve the binding energy, but the effect was not considerable. On the other hand, modifications of the graphene sheet with oxygen atoms and hydroxyl groups led to a drastic increase in the magnitude of binding energies. In all cases, these two types of modifications increased the magnitude of the binding energy, with the presence of hydroxyl groups leading to a dramatic improvement. Specifically, the presence of an OH group led to an increase in the magnitude of the binding energy from 30% to 100% in all cases.

Probably the most important aspect of these results lies in the fact that the highest increase in the magnitude of binding energy due to the functionalization of the graphene nanosheet with OH groups occurred in the case of binding butyric and isobutyric acids, which are VOCs that are particularly difficult to separate by portable MIMS system. Namely, these compounds are

isomers present in the exhaled human breath. They have the same molecular formula ($C_4H_8O_2$) and molecular mass (88.11 g/mol). Also, they have similar boiling points and vapor pressures, which are crucial characteristics for MIMS determination [51,52]. Thus, without previous separation in time, and enabling these compounds to get in the mass analyzer separately, they would provide one peak (or two overlapping peaks) in the mass spectrum. It is important to separate these compounds, as they can provide information about food metabolism. Butyric acid is one of the short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs), which, together with acetic and propionic acids, indicates the intensity of carbohydrates fermentation by gastrointestinal bacteria. Isobutyric acid is one of the branched-chain fatty acids resulting from protein fermentation by bacteria in the gastrointestinal tract [2].

3.4. Study of non-covalent interactions

Considering the significance of non-covalent interactions in molecular detection, this study aims to better understand the binding mechanisms between graphene and VOCs. Noncovalent interactions play a crucial role in determining the affinity and selectivity of molecules, making them essential for accurate and sensitive detection methodologies. We can discover the factors influencing the exceptionally strong binding observed with specific VOCs by exploring and quantifying these interactions.

In order to obtain information about intermolecular interactions between graphene derivatives and selected VOCs, DFT calculations were performed using the B3LYP-D3/MIDIX level of the theory according to the methodologies elaborated in references [53–55]. This choice of level of theory presents a balance between computational cost and accuracy, taking into consideration the size of the systems under investigation. The DFT calculations provide a powerful tool for investigating the non-covalent interactions between graphene and selected VOCs, enabling us to characterize and quantify the strength of these interactions.

The results of our study are visually represented and labeled in Figure 6, providing a clear illustration of the noncovalent interactions between graphene and selected VOCs. Additionally, the corresponding numerical values can be found in Table 2, offering quantitative insights into the strengths of these interactions.

Figure 6. Visualization of the intermolecular noncovalent interactions (blue dashed lines) for the following cases: a) IBA@PPPO, b) ISO@GR, c) ISO@GR-hole, d) IBA@GR-O, e) IBA@GR-OH

In this study, we analyzed noncovalent interactions in graphene-VOC systems for which the strongest binding energies have been calculated. The objective was to understand which noncovalent interactions play a major role in the binding of graphene and its derivatives with selected VOCs. According to the results shown in Figure 5, the VOCs that exhibited the strongest binding were isoprene (**ISO**) and isobutyric acid (**IBA**). **ISO** showed the strongest binding affinity with **GR** and **GR-hole** nanosheets, whereas **IBA** demonstrated the strongest bonding with **PPPO**, **GR-O**, and **GR-OH** nanosheets.

Table 2. Summary of strengths of intermolecular NCI, expressed in electron density (e/bohr³)

NCI#	NCI strength				
	IBA@PPPO	ISO@GR	ISO@GR-hole	IBA@GR-O	IBA@GR-OH
1	-0.0019	-0.0066	-0.0071	-0.0392	-0.0485
2	-0.0056	-0.0070	-0.0090	-0.0116	-0.0313
3	-0.0040	-0.0086	-0.0067	-0.0076	-0.0093
4	-0.0081	-0.0068	/	-0.0057	-0.0084
5	-0.0099	/	/	/	-0.0072
6	-0.0114	/	/	/	/
7	-0.0050	/	/	/	/
8	-0.0165	/	/	/	/
9	-0.0155	/	/	/	/

The highest number of noncovalent interactions was observed in the interaction between **PPPO** and **IBA** VOC, which is expected due to the flexible nature of polymer chains. According to the results presented in Table 2, the two strongest noncovalent interactions, in this case, are denoted by numbers 8 and 9, both involving the hydrogen atom of the OH group of the **IBA** VOC.

In the binding of **ISO** to **GR** and **GR-hole** nanosheets, all noncovalent interactions are characterized by weak strengths, not exceeding 0.001 e/bohr³. This suggests that the binding, in this case, can hardly be attributed to electrostatic interactions.

The most significant situation arises in binding **IBA** to **GR-O** and **GR-OH** graphene nanosheets. In these cases, intense noncovalent interactions emerge, indicating strong electrostatic interactions. In the case of **IBA** binding to **GR-O** (Figure 6d), the strongest noncovalent interaction, denoted as number 1, has a strength of -0.0392 e/bohr³.

However, the strongest noncovalent interaction occurs when **IBA** is bound to the **GR-OH** nanosheet (Figure 6e), also denoted as number 1, with a corresponding strength of -0.0485. In this case, a somewhat weaker but still very strong noncovalent interaction is denoted as number 2, with a corresponding strength of -0.0313 e/bohr³. These strong noncovalent interactions in binding IBA to GR-OH are consistent with the previously calculated binding energies, indicating that a graphene nanosheet decorated with OH groups might serve as a sorbent for this important VOC. Furthermore, a visual inspection of the noncovalent interactions presented in Figure 6e further emphasizes the importance of OH groups in both **GR** and **IBA**, as the strongest interactions involve precisely the atoms of these groups.

3.5. MD simulations – critical temperatures for desorption of isobutyric acid

MD simulations play a crucial role in studying interactions between sorbents and adsorbing molecules, enabling researchers to investigate the dynamic behavior of these systems at the atomic level. One of the most important aspects of MD simulations is that the influence of temperature on the strength of interactions can be taken into account. This fact is essential for the MIMS with TPD, since the desorption of adsorbed compounds is achieved by increasing the temperature. Identifying critical temperature values for compounds' adsorption and desorption is crucial for optimizing the VOCs separation using MIMS with the TPD system.

The detailed analysis of binding energies indicated that the OH-modified graphene nanosheets might bind isobutyric acid molecules much stronger than the **PPPO**. However, this binding should not be too strong to achieve desorption at reasonably high temperatures. In this study, we employed MD simulations to study the radial distribution functions (RDF) between interacting atoms of sorbents and VOC molecules.

For MD simulations, we applied a recently developed GFN force field (GFN-FF), which is characterized by the speed of force field methods and the accuracy that almost reaches the performance of quantum mechanics [44]. This method, implemented in the highly efficient xtb program, enables studying large systems. In terms of MD simulations, we focused on studying the interactions between GR-OH sorbents and isobutyric acid because the strongest binding energies were calculated in this case. We performed a series of MD simulations with a simulation time of 1 ns, in a temperature range between 298 K and 358 K. RDF of system GR-OH and isobutyric acid at different temperatures have been presented in Figure 5.

Figure 7. RDFs between GR-OH and isobutyric acid in a temperature range of a) 298 K – 358 K in steps of 10 K and b) 348 K – 358 K in steps of 1 K

RDF provides a probability of finding a particle at a certain distance from another particle. RDFs presented in Figure 6 have been calculated by considering the distance between the OH atoms of the **GR-OH** and the oxygen and hydrogen atoms of the carboxylic group of the **IBA** acid. First, the MD simulations were performed starting from a room temperature of 298 K in steps of 10 K. After each considered temperature, RDF was plotted, and the MD simulations were run at higher temperatures until the maximal $g(r)$ value dropped. The drop in $g(r)$ values indicates that the **IBA** practically detaches from the OH group and no longer interacts with it.

It can be seen in Figure 6a, that the maximal $g(r)$ values practically stay high until the temperature of 358 K is taken into account. At this temperature, a sudden drop is noticed, indicating that the interactions of isobutyric acid with the OH group of the **GR-OH** drastically decrease. Indeed, the visual inspection of trajectories indicates that at a particular moment of MD simulation at 358 K, the **IBA** molecule detaches from the OH group and relocates to the other surface of the graphene nanosheet with no OH group.

Since the rough temperature step was taken in the first series of MD simulations (10 K), it can be stated that the drastic decrease in interaction between **IBA** and **GR-OH** happens at some temperature between 348 K and 358 K. To identify which temperature was that precisely, we performed another series of MD simulations, in the range from 348 K to 358 K, but with a small temperature step of just 1 K. These results have been presented in Figure 6b. It can be seen that the maximal $g(r)$ value is consistent until the temperature of 358 K is reached. In other words, the drastic drop in the interaction between isobutyric acid and **GR-OH** happens at 358 K.

The results obtained via MD simulations indicate that the **GR-OH** nanosheet might bind **IBA** to the temperature of 358 K. According to the performed MD simulations, once the temperature of 358 K is reached, the sudden drop in interaction strength between **IBA** and **GR-OH** occurs, allowing desorption under temperature that should be easily achieved in the MIMS-TPD system.

4. Conclusions

In this work, an extensive multiscale modeling study involving DFT and semiempirical calculations, along with the MD simulations, has been performed to check whether functionalized graphene nanosheets might have the potential to be applied as sorbents for selected VOC molecules in MIMS coupled with TPD systems. To achieve this aim, we have investigated in detail the interactions between four types of graphene nanosheets and ten VOC molecules. The analysis of reactive properties upon functionalization showed that the **GR-OH** graphene nanosheet is the most sensitive derivative towards the electrostatic interactions with other molecules since the magnitude of the negative MEP values more than tripled compared to the pristine graphene nanosheet. Conversely, the **GR-hole** derivative is the most sensitive

derivative towards electrophilic attacks since the structural deformation of such type led to the drastic decrease of the minimal ALIE value compared to the pristine graphene nanosheet.

Fifty molecular systems were subjected to calculations of binding energies, and the binding energies were compared to the binding energies between the **PPPO** (the main component of a well-known commercially available sorbent known as TENAX[®]) and VOC molecules. Among other facts, the results of binding energies indicate that the functionalization of graphene nanosheet with OH group leads to a significant increase in the strength of binding of VOC molecules. The highest magnitude of binding energy occurred in the case of the binding between **GR-OH** and **IBA**, which was particularly encouraging because this VOC compound is a challenge for our recently developed portable MIMS system. Additionally, the analysis of noncovalent interactions between nanosheets and VOC for systems with the strongest binding energies revealed that the OH group is principally responsible for the strong binding of **IBA** to **GR-OH**. This was a motivation to study this system further.

MD simulations were performed to assess the temperatures suitable for binding to and, even more critical, desorption of the isobutyric acid from **GR-OH**. Applying the GFN-FF method, we have performed 18 MD simulations to calculate RDFs and identify the range of temperatures important for the binding and desorption of **IBA**. According to the sudden drop of the maximal $g(r)$ value, it can be concluded that 358 K might be the critical temperature where the desorption of isobutyric acid might occur. This is an encouraging result because this temperature is easily achievable in our recently developed portable MIMS-TPD system.

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Data availability statement

The data supporting the findings of this study are available upon reasonable request from the corresponding author.

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